

Deep-learning Evaluation for Enhanced Prognostics - Prostate Specific Membrane Antigen: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Deep-learning Evaluation for Enhanced Prognostics - Prostate Specific Membrane Antigen

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

DEEP-PSMA

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Prostate cancer is the most diagnosed and one of the five leading causes of death from cancer. In the advanced form, metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC) has a high rate of mortality with 30% survival at 5 years and, previously, a limited number of effective treatments after progression from hormone therapy. The development of the molecular target, prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA), has enabled new techniques to both image and target systemic disease. Three FDA approved tracers for Positron Emission Tomography (PET) imaging - ^{68}Ga -PSMA-11, ^{18}F -DCFPyL and ^{18}F -rhPSMA-7 - now enable more accurate detection of metastatic spread throughout the body and also selection of patients for radiopharmaceutical therapy (Hofman et al., 2020; Jadvar et al., 2022). Treatment of mCRPC with the ^{177}Lu -PSMA-617 (LuPSMA) presents opportunities to improve quality-of-life and life expectancy in men who have progressed after receiving chemotherapy or hormone therapies (Hofman et al., 2024; Hofman et al., 2021; Sartor et al., 2021).

The expression of targetable receptors in cancer tissues can be quantified by PSMA PET imaging. The addition of FDG PET imaging further informs metabolic activity or hypoxia at the cellular level indicative of an aggressive or potentially poorly responsive form of the disease. Biomarkers from PSMA and FDG imaging have been shown to be predictive of response to ^{177}Lu -PSMA therapy in both the TheraP (Buteau et al., 2022) and LuPSMA trials (Ferdinandus et al., 2020). Ferdinandus et al. reported response classification based on FDG metabolic tumor volume greater or less than 207 ml and PSMA PET SUV_{mean} with a cutoff of 10.55. Buteau et al. retested these baseline predictors in a separate cohort (FDG MTV threshold of 200 ml and PSMA SUV_{mean} of 10). Similar patterns have been observed as lesion-level response predictors (Rosar et al., 2024) showing that PSMA expression is correlated to response and the ratio of FDG expression relative to PSMA uptake is inversely correlated to treatment response. Correlations between mean PSMA PET tumor SUV at staging with progression free survival, overall survival, and PSA response were also reported in the VISION trial (Kuo et al., 2022). Despite PSMA PET representing a strong predictive and prognostic biomarker in LuPSMA therapy, the manual overhead

and lack of robust standardization currently limits routine clinical use.

Existing works applying artificial intelligence methods to mCRPC imaging have yielded promising results, but the reported accuracy has not reached a reliable standard for automated clinical use. Zhao et al. developed a 2.5D U-Net neural network applied to 68Ga-PSMA-11 PET/CT images for scoring total disease volume yielding spatial accuracy of 64.5% for bone lesions and 54.4% for lymph node lesions (Zhao et al., 2020). Using nnU-Net for segmentation of PSMA PET images, Jafari et al. reported lesion level sensitivity exceeding 90%, however volumetric accuracy at voxel level was lower with dice scores in the order of 65-70% (Jafari et al., 2023). Moazemi et al. utilized a similar technique of trained U-Net for whole body disease detection in PSMA PET achieving a similar volumetric accuracy of 0.82 by dice coefficient. In FDG PET imaging, Jemaa et al. have reported dice agreements as high as 0.886 in non-small cell lung cancer (Jemaa et al., 2020). Results from the public FDG imaging challenge dataset, AutoPET, yielded best-performing dice accuracies of approximately 0.8 in a cohort of melanoma, lung cancer, and lymphoma patients (Gatidis et al., 2023).

While previous research has shown promise in automating the analysis of proven image biomarkers for improved patient selection, further refinements are necessary to deliver a methodology that is fit for clinical use. This project aims to harness the open science philosophy to leverage a large institutional dataset and the collective problem-solving capabilities of the medical imaging and computer science communities to deliver a highly impactful improvement in patient care.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

PET/CT, PSMA, FDG, Segmentation

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This is the first challenge aimed at evaluating PET imaging of metastatic prostate cancer. We incorporate two PET modalities which provide complementary functional information and may be utilised simultaneously with novel computational methods that incorporate the information as multiple domains. Biomarkers derived from annotations of disease extent on PSMA and FDG PET imaging have been shown to predict likely responders to targeted Lu-177-PSMA therapy. This is the first AI challenge applied in the context of PET imaging for metastatic prostate cancer with direct implications in disease staging as well as patient selection for targeted therapies.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The task assists with staging of patients for Lu-177 PSMA therapy by determination of quantitative image biomarkers relevant to outcome prediction, namely FDG Total Metabolic Volume (TMV) and PSMA SUVmean.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

25

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Plan to coordinate summary publication of novel and best-performing methods. Have previously participated in FLARE21 challenge and would consider a similar approach for disseminating outcomes.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

We will utilize Grand-Challenge.org platform for submissions, scoring and leaderboard analysis. Have been in discussion with their software team for suitability, attended hosting workshop, and have established landing page at <https://deep-psma.grand-challenge.org/>.

TASK 1: PSMA PET/CT Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Developing new deep learning algorithms to radically improve application of Lutetium-177-PSMA (177Lu-PSMA) theranostics will achieve the best outcomes for patients with metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC). The theranostic approach uniquely affords the ability to “See What You Treat” using positron emission tomography (PET) and single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) before and after therapy. Previously published quantitative biomarkers enable improved patient selection for Lu-177 therapy by designating cases with sufficient PSMA tracer avidity to yield effective radiation delivery to target tissues. This relies on a standardised delineation of total disease extent on PSMA PET at time of staging and assessment of mean intensity of uptake to the full metastatic tumour burden (PSMA SUVmean) with a threshold of 10 stratifying cases with likely biochemical response. We aim to create a fully automated machine learning solution that will match or surpass current labour-intensive human approaches which characterise cancer biology and achieve best patient selection. Results have the potential to enable a transition from a one-size-fits-all to an individualised approach, improving lives for patients with prostate cancer whilst also having direct applicability in a broader range of cancers. This will lead to enhanced outcomes for those impacted by prostate cancer and address disparities in management of prostate cancer by making available tools that can offer the same high-quality precision care at any medical facility capable of PET/CT staging.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

PSMA PET/CT, Segmentation, Tumor Burden, Metastatic

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Price Jackson, Lachlan McIntosh, James Buteau, Michael Hofman

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Price Jackson, price.jackson@petermac.org, +61 385598729

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://deep-psma.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

In discussion internally, but tentative shared leaderboard between Tasks 1 & 2. Single leaderboard overall with winning submission earning ~2000 EUR, Ranks 2-3 1000 EUR, and 4-5 500 EUR.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 5 methods will be announced publicly

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)

- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Each of the top 5 teams qualifies for the challenge publication with up to two contributing authors from each. Teams may publish their own results separately.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission (type 2) on Grand Challenge.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Recommended by grand challenge to allow one final submission on test data to be scored

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Tentative schedule: Release of Training Cases and Registration April 2025, Release of Validation Cases and Temporary Leaderboard June 2025, Release of final Test Cases July 2025, Final Submission Date Sept 2025. Release of Results at MICCAI 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval required and in process with our institutional review board. All image data is from patients who have previously consented to research use of image data. All images have been previously acquired and provided expert annotations from expert clinician staff members.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY (Attribution)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We have established a repository associated with the challenge for information around image pre- and post-processing as well as a sample submission based on our institutional AI models (<https://github.com/Peter-MacCallum-Cancer-Centre/DEEP-PSMA>). This will include the scoring scripts to be run on grand-challenge backend to facilitate submission QC by entrants prior to entering on the platform. Additionally, we have developed an institutional baseline model which incorporates a number of task-specific refinements on nnU-Net (<https://github.com/jacksonmedphysics/GTRC-Net>) for adaptation by entrants.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Eligibility for challenge awards and consideration of final leaderboard is contingent on making entrant code publicly available. Review of submission training and inference code is also required to verify that performance is based on only provided challenge dataset.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Funding for challenge has been provided by Prostate Cancer Foundation but no commercial conflicts-of-interest apply

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education

- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients with metastatic castrate-resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC) staged prior to treatment with Lu-177 PSMA therapy. PSMA PET imaging is largely specific to this cohort with limited applicability to other cancer types.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort in this project is patients with mCRPC staged prior to treatment with Lu-177 PSMA therapy.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

PSMA PET/CT Imaging

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Image Data - PET and CT fused modalities with expert annotation of total metastatic disease extent based on standardized threshold workflow with manual mark-up.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other additional information provided, though each patient will have one PSMA PET/CT and one FDG PET/CT which may be utilized simultaneously as a potential method refinement. PSMA and FDG images are acquired separately and no specific image registration will be applied prior.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with metastatic castrate-resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC) staged prior to treatment with Lu-177 PSMA therapy. PET scans (PET and low-dose CT component) acquired generally from head to mid femur. In cases with disease in extremities, scan extent may include lower limbs.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Metastatic disease with potential location in the whole-body. Majority of scans are from head to thighs with some extended scan lengths for metastatic spread to the lower limbs. Cases will often have multiple sites of disease but all captured in a single, Total tumor volume, annotation as task target.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Diagnostic PET/CT systems. Predominantly from institutional scanners GE Discovery 710 & 690 PET/CTs, Siemens Biograph PET/CT, and Siemens Vision 600 PET/CT

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Whole body (predominantly vertex to thighs) PET images with low-dose CT component for attenuation correction and anatomical localization. PET images reconstructed with standard corrections EANM EARL-compliant resolution recovery settings.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, Melbourne, Australia

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Images acquired by nuclear medicine technologists and reviewed by specialist nuclear medicine physicians. Annotations of disease extent provided by NM physicians using standardized threshold workflow on image review software with manual mark-up to discriminate malignant versus physiological areas of tracer uptake.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and Test cases both represent one PSMA PET/CT and one FDG PET/CT each with their own tracer-specific annotation of total disease extent.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

100 training, 5 validation, 45 testing

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

150 cases in total have been prepared. From discussion with the grand challenge team, a small number of validation cases are required to verify compatibility of entrant docker containers (advised 3 cases) and leave sufficient amount for testing to ensure models are generalizable over a modest population.

On advice from MICCAI reviews, the volume of testing cases has been increased from 25 to 45 in order to reduce the risk of overfitting or limited statistical strength to stratify leaderboard.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All cases will have some presence of disease for contouring but there will be a distribution of large- and small-volume cases and various patterns of metastatic spread (eg largely osseous, nodal, liver-involvement, etc). We have considered a balance of training and test cases that will account for a similar distribution of case patterns based on manual selection.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All data is previously unseen outside of our institution

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

All images (training, validation, & testing) have been previously annotated by an expert clinician using the same image review software and contouring workflow.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Annotations are marked up the same for training validation and test cases. In each PET/CT image, all voxels greater than equal to SUV 3 delineated by threshold. Subsequently, areas of physiological (non-disease) uptake such as kidneys and bladder were manually painted out leaving only areas of disease confined to the specified PET intensity range (SUV ≥ 3).

Manual annotation workflow described in: 1. Buteau JP, Martin AJ, Emmett L, Iravani A, Sandhu S, Joshua AM, et al. PSMA and FDG-PET as predictive and prognostic biomarkers in patients given [177Lu] Lu-PSMA-617 versus cabazitaxel for metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (TheraP): a biomarker analysis from a randomised, open-label, phase 2 trial. *The Lancet Oncology*. 2022;23(11):1389-97.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All images marked up by specialist nuclear medicine physicians with at least 5 years experience in clinical molecular imaging.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Multiple annotations will not be merged for cases

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

PET/CT images are acquired in DICOM format and intensity of the PET images converted from units of Bq/ml to standardized uptake value (SUV). Annotations are initially provided as DICOM RTSTRUCT format and point cloud contours converted into label map and matched to resolution of input PET 3D volume. Both PET and CT images are converted into ITK format (.mha) to facilitate processing tasks. Similarly, annotation label map provided as .mha in label map matched to PET spatial array. CT image may be provided in both original (high) resolution and downsampled to match PET origin, direction, and spacing.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Degree of interobserver variability is generally less than 1% given the constraint of segmentation based on image SUV thresholds with a small proportion of label boundaries occurring at the interface of malignant and avid uptake which requires manual in/out-painting. Areas near liver, ureters, and other sites of common physiologic uptake are most challenging but a limited proportion of the overall disease patterns across cases.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

We have developed data QC processes to verify the accuracy of PET SUV data, conversion of annotation point clouds to label maps and use of appropriate thresholds. All post-processed images and annotations are reviewed visually and a selection of cases have been flagged for manual re-review. We have also assessed the performance of our baseline AI model and all poorly-performing cases have undergone manual review of the ground-truth label as a secondary means of identifying erroneous or unreliable data.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

For the segmentation task which frequently includes many sites of metastatic spread in each training case we consider an adapted criteria from the AutoPET challenges. We consider total tumour volume Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) as well as connected-component false-positive and false negative volume (<https://github.com/lab-midas/autoPET>). Given the task has specific focus on matching the standardised threshold

workflow for measuring imaging biomarkers of PSMA SUVmean and FDG metabolic tumour volume which are both sensitive to the inclusion or omission of voxels near the boundary surface, we will also record Surface Dice and Normalised Surface Dice.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Dice score is ubiquitous for assessment of image segmentation accuracy. Other distance metrics (Hausdorff distance, mean distance to agreement) are not always suitable for annotation of multiple disease sites as in whole body PET imaging. May consider median distance to agreement though not as reliable in this instance where small volumetric omission (exclusion of small metastatic site) might yield an unrepresentative DTA error. Could also compute surface Dice (Dice constrained to surface voxels on ground truth and inferred annotations) sDice takes account of how much modification a clinician needs to make to correct a model output. It's very close to a working scenario. The only problem is for incorrect predictions on small lesions (imagine translation of the label by a few voxels), the correction required is minor since the entire surface is small. Hence nsDice can fill this gap by measuring the fraction.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

A weighted average of dice and surface dice metrics will be used with an additional penalty for false positive and negative volume according to the AutoPET criteria.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results considered zero dice score and will yield predictably unbiased low performance scores for affected cases on the leaderboard.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Dice is most common metric for scoring image segmentation accuracy which accounts for false positive/negative volumes relative to true positive volume. Additional metrics including distance to agreement were tested but were not considered suitable for evaluation of metastatic disease distribution. Instead surface Dice and normalized surface Dice are recorded as a surrogate for the amount of manual user input required to correct inferred labels to the appropriate boundary location for quantitative biomarker assessment.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

All cases included in the challenge design have some volume of measurable disease to enable DSC and other metrics to be evaluated. All images (training, validation, testing) have undergone QC and evaluation with baseline institutional model to verify suitability for analysis. Submissions that cannot complete processing or do not label

any voxels will yield metric scores of zero for the respective cases but with otherwise not adversely bias the overall ranking result. Wilcoxon signed rank test will be used to assess the ranking and bootstrapping used to determine variability.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Wilcoxon test provides a means to test significance for improvement between submissions which are testable based on simple hypotheses.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is for statistical hypothesis testing used for testing the location of a population based on a sample of data. This is suitable for accessing the rank of a submission among all submissions.

TASK 2: FDG PET/CT Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

As above in description of Task 1, the assessment of disease extent at time of staging is a predictor of treatment outcome to therapy. In the case of FDG PET imaging, assessment of total disease extent (metabolic tumour volume) is a marker of the size of aggressive, or actively populating, cancer cells. In studies utilising FDG at staging prior to Lu-177 PSMA therapy, a metabolic disease extent greater than 200cc has been linked to poorer outcomes. In tandem, assessment of functional characteristics of disease as well as the distribution of metastatic spread and spatial concordance of tracer expression between FDG and PSMA tracers enable powerful classification of disease phenotype. This first stage, focuses on the delineation of disease extent with each of the two PET tracers and we hope to incorporate spatial fusion and multi-modal image biomarker improvements to future challenges which may be used to objectively assess concordance and novel engineered image biomarkers.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

FDG PET/CT, Segmentation, Tumor Burden, Metastatic

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Price Jackson, Lachlan McIntosh, James Buteau, Michael Hofman

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Price Jackson, price.jackson@petermac.org, +61 385598729

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One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

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MICCAI 2025

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grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://deep-psma.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

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Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

In discussion internally, but tentative shared leaderboard between Tasks 1 & 2. Single leaderboard overall with winning submission earning ~2000 EUR, Ranks 2-3 1000 EUR, and 4-5 500 EUR.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 5 methods will be announced publicly

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Each of the top 5 teams qualifies for the challenge publication with up to two contributing authors from each. Teams may publish their own results separately.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission (type 2) on Grand Challenge.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Recommended by grand challenge to allow one final submission on test data to be scored

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Tentative schedule: Release of Training Cases and Registration April 2025, Release of Validation Cases and Temporary Leaderboard June 2025, Release of final Test Cases July 2025, Final Submission Date Sept 2025. Release of Results at MICCAI 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval required and in process with our institutional review board. All image data is from patients who have previously consented to research use of image data. All images have been previously acquired and provided expert annotations from expert clinician staff members.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY (Attribution)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We have established a repository associated with the challenge for information around image pre- and post-processing as well as a sample submission based on our institutional AI models (<https://github.com/Peter-MacCallum-Cancer-Centre/DEEP-PSMA>). This will include the scoring scripts to be run on grand-challenge backend to facilitate submission QC by entrants prior to entering on the platform. Additionally, we have developed an institutional baseline model which incorporates a number of task-specific refinements on nnU-Net (<https://github.com/jacksonmedphysics/GTRC-Net>) for adaptation by entrants.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Eligibility for challenge awards and consideration of final leaderboard is contingent on making entrant code publicly available. Review of submission training and inference code is also required to verify that performance is based on only provided challenge dataset.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Funding for challenge has been provided by Prostate Cancer Foundation but no commercial conflicts-of-interest apply

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research

- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

FDG PET is a common diagnostic modality for oncologic staging and the task may have some applicability to other cancer phenotypes but for this challenge the target cohort is mCRPC. While the pattern of physiological tracer uptake for discrimination is consistent for all FDG PET imaging uses, the most common distributions of metastatic spread in mCRPC is unique to the disease in comparison to, for example, lymphoma or NSCLC.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort in this project is patients with mCRPC staged prior to treatment with Lu-177 PSMA therapy.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

FDG PET/CT Imaging

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Image Data - PET and CT fused modalities with expert annotation of total metastatic disease extent based on standardized threshold workflow with manual mark-up.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other additional information provided, though each patient will have one PSMA PET/CT and one FDG PET/CT which may be utilized simultaneously as a potential method refinement. PSMA and FDG images are acquired separately and no specific image registration will be applied prior.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with metastatic castrate-resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC) staged prior to treatment with Lu-177 PSMA therapy. PET scans (PET and low-dose CT component) acquired generally from head to mid femur. In cases with disease in extremities, scan extent may include lower limbs.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Metastatic disease with potential location in the whole-body. Majority of scans are from head to thighs with some extended scan lengths for metastatic spread to the lower limbs. Cases will often have multiple sites of disease but all captured in a single, Total tumor volume, annotation as task target.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Diagnostic PET/CT systems. Predominantly from institutional scanners GE Discovery 710 & 690 PET/CTs, Siemens Biograph PET/CT, and Siemens Vision 600 PET/CT

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Whole body (predominantly vertex to thighs) PET images with low-dose CT component for attenuation correction and anatomical localization. PET images reconstructed with standard corrections EANM EARL-compliant resolution recovery settings.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, Melbourne, Australia

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Images acquired by nuclear medicine technologists and reviewed by specialist nuclear medicine physicians. Annotations of disease extent provided by NM physicians using standardized threshold workflow on image review software with manual mark-up to discriminate malignant versus physiological areas of tracer uptake.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and Test cases both represent one PSMA PET/CT and one FDG PET/CT each with their own tracer-specific annotation of total disease extent.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

100 training, 5 validation, 45 testing

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

150 cases in total have been prepared. From discussion with the grand challenge team, a small number of validation cases are required to verify compatibility of entrant docker containers (advised 3 cases) and leave

sufficient amount for testing to ensure models are generalizable over a modest population.

On advice from MICCAI reviews, the volume of testing cases has been increased from 25 to 45 in order to reduce the risk of overfitting or limited statistical strength to stratify leaderboard.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All cases will have some presence of disease for contouring but there will be a distribution of large- and small-volume cases and various patterns of metastatic spread (eg largely osseous, nodal, liver-involvement, etc). We have considered a balance of training and test cases that will account for a similar distribution of case patterns based on manual selection.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All data is previously unseen outside of our institution

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

All images (training, validation, & testing) have been previously annotated by an expert clinician using the same image review software and contouring workflow.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Annotations are marked up the same for training validation and test cases. In each PET/CT image, all voxels greater than equal to SUV 3 delineated by threshold. Subsequently, areas of physiological (non-disease) uptake such as kidneys and bladder were manually painted out leaving only areas of disease confined to the specified PET intensity range (SUV ≥ 3).

Manual annotation workflow described in: 1. Buteau JP, Martin AJ, Emmett L, Iravani A, Sandhu S, Joshua AM, et al. PSMA and FDG-PET as predictive and prognostic biomarkers in patients given [177Lu] Lu-PSMA-617 versus cabazitaxel for metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (TheraP): a biomarker analysis from a randomised, open-label, phase 2 trial. *The Lancet Oncology*. 2022;23(11):1389-97.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All images marked up by specialist nuclear medicine physicians with at least 5 years experience in clinical molecular imaging.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Multiple annotations will not be merged for cases

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

PET/CT images are acquired in DICOM format and intensity of the PET images converted from units of Bq/ml to standardized uptake value (SUV). Annotations are initially provided as DICOM RTSTRUCT format and point cloud contours converted into label map and matched to resolution of input PET 3D volume. Both PET and CT images are converted into ITK format (.mha) to facilitate processing tasks. Similarly, annotation label map provided as .mha in label map matched to PET spatial array. CT image may be provided in both original (high) resolution and downsampled to match PET origin, direction, and spacing.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Degree of interobserver variability is generally less than 1% given the constraint of segmentation based on image SUV thresholds with a small proportion of label boundaries occurring at the interface of malignant and avid uptake which requires manual in/out-painting. Areas near liver, ureters, and other sites of common physiologic uptake are most challenging but a limited proportion of the overall disease patterns across cases.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

We have developed data QC processes to verify the accuracy of PET SUV data, conversion of annotation point clouds to label maps and use of appropriate thresholds. All post-processed images and annotations are reviewed visually and a selection of cases have been flagged for manual re-review. We have also assessed the performance of our baseline AI model and all poorly-performing cases have undergone manual review of the ground-truth label as a secondary means of identifying erroneous or unreliable data.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

For the segmentation task which frequently includes many sites of metastatic spread in each training case we consider an adapted criteria from the AutoPET challenges. We consider total tumour volume Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) as well as connected-component false-positive and false negative volume (<https://github.com/lab-midas/autoPET>). Given the task has specific focus on matching the standardised threshold workflow for measuring imaging biomarkers of PSMA SUVmean and FDG metabolic tumour volume which are both sensitive to the inclusion or omission of voxels near the boundary surface, we will also record Surface Dice and Normalised Surface Dice.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Dice score is ubiquitous for assessment of image segmentation accuracy. Other distance metrics (Hausdorff distance, mean distance to agreement) are not always suitable for annotation of multiple disease sites as in whole body PET imaging. May consider median distance to agreement though not as reliable in this instance where small volumetric omission (exclusion of small metastatic site) might yield an unrepresentative DTA error. Could also compute surface Dice (Dice constrained to surface voxels on ground truth and inferred annotations) sDice takes account of how much modification a clinician needs to make to correct a model output. It's very close to a working scenario. The only problem is for incorrect predictions on small lesions (imagine translation of the label by a few voxels), the correction required is minor since the entire surface is small. Hence nsDice can fill this gap by measuring the fraction.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

A weighted average of dice and surface dice metrics will be used with an additional penalty for false positive and negative volume according to the AutoPET criteria.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results considered zero dice score and will yield predictably unbiased low performance scores for affected cases on the leaderboard.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Dice is most common metric for scoring image segmentation accuracy which accounts for false positive/negative volumes relative to true positive volume. Additional metrics including distance to agreement were tested but were not considered suitable for evaluation of metastatic disease distribution. Instead surface Dice and normalized surface Dice are recorded as a surrogate for the amount of manual user input required to correct inferred labels to the appropriate boundary location for quantitative biomarker assessment.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

All cases included in the challenge design have some volume of measurable disease to enable DSC and other metrics to be evaluated. All images (training, validation, testing) have undergone QC and evaluation with baseline institutional model to verify suitability for analysis. Submissions that cannot complete processing or do not label any voxels will yield metric scores of zero for the respective cases but with otherwise not adversely bias the overall ranking result. Wilcoxon signed rank test will be used to assess the ranking and bootstrapping used to determine variability.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Wilcoxon test provides a means to test significance for improvement between submissions which are testable based on simple hypotheses.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is for statistical hypothesis testing used for testing the location of a population based on a sample of data. This is suitable for accessing the rank of a submission among all submissions.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

Manual Annotation workflow based on fixed (PSMA) or liver-based (FDG) SUV thresholds described in: Buteau JP, Martin AJ, Emmett L, Iravani A, Sandhu S, Joshua AM, et al. PSMA and FDG-PET as predictive and prognostic biomarkers in patients given [177Lu] Lu-PSMA-617 versus cabazitaxel for metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (TheraP): a biomarker analysis from a randomised, open-label, phase 2 trial. *The Lancet Oncology*. 2022;23(11):1389-97.

We have adapted evaluation metrics from the AutoPET grand challenges which includes DSC as well as a connected component false positive/negative analysis. All metrics including an additional surface Dice are made available at <https://github.com/Peter-MacCallum-Cancer-Centre/DEEP-PSMA>

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

We greatly appreciate the opportunity to revise our previous submission as well as the time and consideration provided by the previous reviewers to improve its content. We have finalized data preparation for the challenge and working through the final logistical steps to be prepared for data release. Additionally, our challenge page has been established on the grand challenge domain and we have allocated time over the coming months for nuclear medicine physicians and our team of image analysis experts to provide support and troubleshooting as the project goes live.